

The highly complex kinematics of the local field stars: young stars, old stars, stellar streams, and all that mix

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Abstract

Abstract. This presentation was part of the splinter session "Brown Dwarfs, Low-Mass Stars, and Directly Imaged Exoplanets in the Era of Gaia". It is primarily a pedagogical demonstration of the level of detail one can obtain about the local kinematics of nearby stars in the era of GAIA parallaxes and radial velocities. It is also a warning that the velocity-space distribution of local field stars is surprisingly inhomogeneous and rich in substructure at the 5-10km/s scale. Most of that inhomogeneities are not the signature of nearby star clusters, or nearby moving groups, but are rather the signature of dynamical instabilities in the disk of the Galaxy, the same instabilities that are responsible for the formation of the Galactic spiral arms. As a striking demonstration of this cause-and-effect relationship, it is shown that the inhomogeneous structure is almost entirely in the local U-V velocity plane, where U is the component of motion in the direction of the Galactic center, and V is in the direction of the Sun's orbital motion in the Galaxy. In ant case, this rich substructure in velocity space can fool analytical tools that are use to search for nearby young moving groups, as inhomogeneities cause by dynamical instabilities can mimic the signature of a moving group. Some ideas are suggested for revealing additional substructure in the local velocity-space distribution of field Galactic stars.

1 Introduction: velocity-space formalism.

First let's go through a pedagogical discussion of the concept of "velocity space". Figure 1 is a schematic description of a distribution of stars in the local field, equivalent to the description of the thermal motion of particles in the kinetic theory of gases. Each star can be described by a specific location in space, and by a velocity vector which describes its motion in space. For a uniform distribution of stars inside a volume, stars are uniformly distribution in position space, but not in velocity space. For thermal-like motions, the statistical distribution of stars in velocity space can be represented by a Maxwellian distribution, which has a maximum value at (0,0) - the "local standard of rest" - and is characterized by a velocity space scatter, i.e. the field "temperature".

The picture for stars in the Galactic field is usually much more complex. Figure 2 shows what happens when one group of stars tend to have similar motions; in that case, the velocity-space distribution will be combination of a "smooth", broad Maxwellian distribution, and of an over-dense "clump" representing the moving group.

Finally, stars in the Galaxy often consist of two or more overlapping populations, for example populations of young stars that are mixed in with stars of older generations. These populations often have distinct kinematics. Young stars are typically found to have smaller average velocities relative to the local standard of rest, while older stars have significantly larger average velocities. This is represented in Figure.3, which shows two overlapping population of young and old stars. Because of the different values of their scatter in velocity space, young stars tend to be over-represented at low velocities, while old stars tend to be over-represented at large velocities. Although the two populations actually overlap in velocity space, this is very often used in astronomy to iden-

Figure 1: Left: Illustration of stars in position space, with their motions represented by vectors; the motions are assumed to be random and described by a Maxwellian distribution. Right: resulting statistical distribution in velocity space. This would be the observed distribution for a large number of stars.

tify subsets of "young" and "old" stars based on their local kinematics. This is however only valid in a statistical sense, and being old does not preclude a star from have a low velocity relative to the local standard of rest, for example.

2 Local velocity-space distribution based on GAIA data

With the GAIA second data release, we now have the coordinates, parallaxes, proper motions, and redial velocities for a large number of stars in the vicinity of the Sun. These observables provide estimates of the stars spatial location and

Figure 2: Left: Same as in Figure 1, but this time the statistical distribution of velocities is described by two components, a broad distribution centered on $(0,0)$, representative of "field stars" (red color), and a clustered distribution at a specific velocity, representing a "moving group" (blue color). The stars in the moving group are clustered only in velocity space, and not in the space of positions.

Figure 3: Left: Same as in Figure 1, but this time the "field" distribution consists of two distinct groups of stars, a "young" component with low velocity scatter, and an "old" component with large velocity scatter. While the two distributions technically overlap, young stars are over-represented at low velocities, and old stars are over-represented at high velocities. This is often used in Galactic astronomy to select subsets of old and young stars for further study.

Figure 4: HR diagram of the 1,755,319 stars in the GAIA DR2 catalog that have inferred distances < 200 pc, and parallax uncertainties $< 10\%$. The 353,065 stars for which radial velocity data is also available are shown in black; they mostly consist of G and K dwarfs.

3D components of motion. The large number of stars for which this is available makes it possible to determine their statistical distribution in velocity space. Or at least this is possible for certain classes of stars. Figure 4 shows the HR diagram of all stars in the GAIA DR2 with parallaxes placing the stars within a distance of 200pc from the Sun; we only keep the stars whose parallaxes are advertised to be better than 10% accurate. This leaves a total number of 1,755,319 stars (all points). Of these, radial velocity measurement are available in the DR2 for only a subset of 353,065 stars (represented in black). Their distribution in the color-magnitude diagram show that these are mostly G and K dwarfs, with a limited number of red giants and subgiants, and relatively few M dwarfs.

This subset of 353,065 local stars, for which the full spatial and velocity-space distribution can be mapped, is remarkable in that it is more than an order of magnitude large than previous samples of fully characterized local stars, for example the catalog of $\approx 14,000$ F and G dwarfs from the Hipparcos catalog for which radial velocities were measured (Nordstrom et al. 2004). The general trends in the velocity space distribution are however found to be similar, as can be seen in Fig.5 (which can be compared to Fig.20 in Nordstrom et al.). These plots show projections of the full 3D distribution along three orthogonal planes, which are defined from the orientation of the Galactic coordinate system $[l,b]$. We calculate the component U representing the motion in the direction of the Galactic center $[l,b]=[0,0]$, component V representing the motion in the direction of Galactic orbital motion of the local standard of rest $[l,b]=[+90,0]$, and component W representing the motion perpendicular to the plane of the Milky Way $[l,b]=[0,+90]$. The distribution of motions in $[U,W]$ show a

Figure 5: Projections of the velocity-space distribution of local field stars along three planes: $[U,W]$, $[V,W]$, and $[U,V]$, where U is the component of motion in the direction of the Galactic center, V is the component of motion in the direction of the Galactic orbital motion for the local standard of rest, and W is the component of motion in the direction of the north Galactic pole, i.e. perpendicular to the plane of the Milky Way. The $[U,W]$ distribution is clearly asymmetric, revealing a much smaller scatter in the motions perpendicular to the plane, which is consistent with vertical confinement of stars in the Galactic disk. The $[V,W]$ distribution reveals the asymmetric drift, with most stars "lagging behind" the local standard of rest, due to their Galactic orbits being non-circular. The $[U,V]$ distribution reveals a remarkable level of "clumpiness"; this velocity-space substructure is best understood as the signature of orbital resonances in the disk of the Galaxy, the same that are responsible for creating the spiral arms.

much smaller scatter of velocities perpendicular to the plane of the Galaxy, which is consistent with the confinement of stars in the Galactic disk; stars with $|W| > 50$ km/s are typically associated kinematically with the thick/old disk or with the Galactic halo. In the $[V,W]$ projection, we see the signature of the "asymmetric drift", which shows most stars lagging behind the Sun in the V component of motion. The lag-guards are stars with more eccentric Galactic orbits, whereas we usually assume that the local standard of rest is defined by a circular orbit around the Galaxy, and along the plane of the Milky way. Most extraordinary is the projection in the $[U,V]$ plane, which shows a remarkable level of substructure. The larger features were previously known, and identified as four general "streams": the Sirius stream, Coma stream, Hyades stream, and Hercules stream (again see Nordstrom et al. 2004). With the GAIA data, we now see that each one of those general streams actually appears to break down in a number of "streamlets", each with an irregular shape. Some of the "clumps" have details at the 5-10 km/s level.

The best interpretation for this intricate substructure in the $[U,V]$ plane is not that these are the signature of clusters, or moving groups of relatively homogeneous stars, for example stars from dissociated clusters that might all have the same age and chemical composition. Rather, the best interpretation for this substructure is that it is the signature of dynamical instabilities in the disk of the Galaxy, the same instabilities that are responsible for creating the Galactic spiral arms. One needs to look at the N-body simulations of, e.g., Quillen et al. (2011); these show that instabilities can develop on timescales of 100 Myr, and grow into resonant patterns in the stellar orbits that create both spiral patterns (in the spatial distribution) and local streams as observed in the GAIA data (in the velocity space distribution). Velocity space patterns predicted by the models are extremely similar to the patterns

observed in the local velocity space distribution; compare our Figure 5 to Figure 8 in Quillen et al.

What these N-body simulations also suggest is that the velocity-space patterns are also very local, and vary significantly as one probes different spatial locations in the galaxy. The patterns show both a variation with radial distance from the center of the galaxy, and variations in the azimuthal direction. One might expect this from the radial and azimuthal variations that create spiral patterns. An important consequence is that this spatial variation means that the size of the volume that is surveyed to build the velocity-space distribution matters a lot. If one selected a relatively large volume, details in the velocity space substructure will be blurred as one will be mixing populations from different locations. Hence the subset of 353,065 stars used in Fig.5 combines stars spread over a relatively large bubble or 200pc radius. If one reduced the size of the spatial volume that is surveyed, one finds a more intricate level of detail that was smoothed out in the larger volume. This is illustrated in Figure 6, which shows the $[U,V]$ projection of the velocity space distribution for two smaller volumes. One ("Location A") consists of a 1.2-million cubic parsec volume located 100 parsecs from the Sun in the direction of Galactic center, the other one ("Location B") consists of a similar 1.2-million cubic parsec volume located 100 parsecs from the Sun in the direction away from the Galactic center. Each sample shows slightly different patterns in the velocity space distribution, noticeable from a careful comparison of the two figures (more apparent if the two plots are blinked in succession). At both location, one may notice clumps that have sizes of only a few km/s in velocity space.

Why does this matter? Because one of the goals of studying the local kinematics of stars is the identification of previously overlooked star clusters and associations, and nearby young moving groups (NYMGs) which are likely the dissoci-

Figure 6: Intricate details in the velocity distribution can be enhanced by examining very local subsets. The two diagrams above plot the $[U,V]$ distributions for two sub-volumes, one located 100pc closer to the Galactic center as measured from the Sun ($X=-100\text{pc}$), and one located 100pc further away from the galactic center ($X=+100\text{pc}$). Note the differences in the substructure patterns; this shows that the velocity-space signature of the orbital resonances is a strong function of the spatial location. As a result, mapping the velocity space distribution using stars spread over a large volume tends to "blur" the substructure, which can lead one to believe that this substructure is not as intricate as it is actually is. Compare with the rightmost panel in Figure 5.

ated stars created in recent, local star formation events (e.g. Gagne et al. 2018). But if one want to identify these moving groups based on the kinematics, one also has to be aware that the velocity space distribution of normal field stars is also extremely inhomogeneous in the $[U,V]$ plane, and shows a surprising level of clumping. As a result, one might associate stars because they share similar motions, even at the $\pm 5\text{ km/s}$ level, but these stars might in fact have very little in common.

3 Conclusions

In this simple exploration of the 3D kinematics of $> 300,00$ nearby stars ($d < 200\text{pc}$) determined from astrometric and radial velocity measurements made by GAIA, we show that the velocity space distribution of local stars is remarkably inhomogeneous. This is of extreme interest for the field of Galactic structure, and details in the velocity space substructure is the signature of large-scale patterns (e.g. spiral arms) in our Galaxy. This however makes more difficult the task of identifying local stars clusters and young moving groups, as they don't stand out so much in velocity space against this very inhomogeneous background of field stars. The current sample of stars with fully determined components of motion remains limited because radial velocity measurements from GAIA have only been released for limited numbers of stars. As more radial velocity data becomes available - especially for the very numerous M dwarfs - more intricate detail may be revealed in the velocity space distribution of local stars.

References

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